

MODELING OF MESO-SCALE VOID FORMATION IN AN ARBITRARY RESIN IMPREGNATION ANGLE OF VARTM

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ABSTRACT

Voids are known to form during resin impregnation in vacuum-assisted resin transfer molding (VaRTM) depending on the resin flow velocity. Since the presence of the voids deteriorates the composites mechanical properties, prediction of the void generation is required. The purpose of this study is to evaluate the effect of the resin impregnation angle in an anisotropic fabric on the relationship between the amount of voids formed and the resin velocity. We performed experimental 2D radial-injection VaRTM and evaluated the void fraction and the void formation mechanism for an anisotropically plain-woven fabric. The relationship between the void fraction and the resin flow velocity for a resin impregnation angle was determined. On the basis of the experimental results, we developed an analytical model for predicting the void fraction for resin impregnation angle and resin flow velocity. Structure of a plane woven fabric is simplified into continuity of the unit cell. Void content is considered to be the ratios of the channel inter bundles that have not filled with resin before intra bundles are filled. The relationship between the void content and the impregnation velocity is predicted to differ in an arbitrary resin-impregnation angle. The predictions of the model were compared with experimental results and good agreement was observed.

1 INTRODUCTION

Vacuum-assisted resin transfer molding (VaRTM) attracts attention as the low-cost composites material molding method to turn into a Autoclave method [1-3]. However, the impregnation of VaRTM may be insufficient because inhomogeneity of fabrics used as a reinforcements [4, 5]. The poor resin impregnation causes the formation of voids, which decreases the strength of the product [6-8]. The voids formed during the impregnation may be classified as macro-scale voids, meso-scale voids, and micro-scale voids depending on their size. Macro-scale void is called a dry spot and is formed in the domain where the fabric is not impregnated by the resin owing to inappropriate setting of the molding conditions such as the resin infusion point [9-11]. Meso-scale void is one caused by inter-bundle air trapping resulting from differences between the high intra-bundle resin flow velocities and low inter-bundle resin flow velocities [12-14]. Micro-scale voids are thus formed by the air trapped in the bundles owing to the difference between the intra-bundle and inter-bundle resin flow velocities, which are respectively slow and fast [13, 15, 16]. Macro-scale voids are larger than meso-scale and micro-scale voids, and whereas impregnation appears to be macroscopically completed in the case of the former, voids are still present in the fabric.

Various studies have been conducted on the inhibition of the formation of these voids. Regarding the inhibition of macro-scale voids, many simulation studies have been conducted to determine the optimal gate location [17-19]. Unlike macro-scale voids, meso-scale and micro-scale voids are caused by unevenness of the microstructure of the fabric. Previous studies have shown that their occurrence depends on only the Capillary number, and numerical models for predicting the void fraction have been developed [13, 20-22]. However, none of the foregoing studies considered the effect of the angle

of the resin impregnation on void formation; only the relationship between the resin flow velocity and the void formation in 1D resin impregnation in the warp or weft direction has been investigated. During resin impregnation in a real structure, the resin flows through the fabric at an arbitrary angle owing to the complexity of the fabric structure and the resin infusion point, and it is therefore necessary to evaluate the effect of the impregnation angle on void formation. In addition, the resin impregnation path through the microscopic structure of the fabric changes with the resin impregnation angle, and there may be a value of the angle that reduces the void fraction more than the warp or weft direction does.

Hence, the purpose of this study was to evaluate the effect of the resin impregnation angle in the fabric on the relationship between the amount of voids formed and the resin velocity. An anisotropically woven fabric was used as the specimen, and evaluated the effect of the void fraction on the formation of meso-scale voids during resin impregnation during 2D radial injection VaRTM. Henceforth in this paper, void refers to meso-scale void. Based on the experiments, analytical model developed for predicting the void fraction for an arbitrary resin impregnation angle in the fabric. The developed model was validated by comparing its predictions with experimental results.

2 VOID OBSERVATION IN 2D RADIAL-INJECTION VARTM

2.1 2D radial-injection VaRTM

To evaluate the relationship between the resin flow velocity and the void fraction during resin impregnation at an arbitrary angle in a fabric, we performed experimental 2D radial injection VaRTM from the center of the fabric. Fig. 1 is a schematic of the experimental device. A one-layer glass fabric was inserted between the upper glass mold and the bottom glass mold. Table 1 gives the material properties of the fabric used for the experiments, namely, M155K104 (Unitika Glass Fiber, henceforth referred to as M155). The material properties of the unsaturated polyester resin (DH material, Sundhoma PC184-C) are given in Table 2. In addition, the impregnation angle of the resin was set to 0° in the warp direction of the fabric, and 90° in the weft direction. In the illustration in Fig. 1, the resin impregnation direction is denoted by \mathbf{n} . The resin impregnation angle θ was defined as the angle between the warp direction and the resin impregnation direction \mathbf{n} . The vacuum pressure P_{vac} during the experiments was set to 50 kPa.

To evaluate the effect of the impregnation direction on the relationship between the resin flow velocity and the void fraction, the void fraction was observed for various impregnation angles. We used a microscope (Keyence VHX-900) to photograph the fabric after the flow front had passed at an arbitrary angle. The photographic images were digitally processed to extract the outline of the voids and measure the void fraction. The voids were columnar, and it was assumed that the 2D void fraction measured by image analysis was equal to the void volume fraction [23].

Figure 1 Schematic of 2D radial-injection VaRTM experiment

Table 1 Material properties of fabric.

Property	Value (SD)
Macroscopic porosity of fabric, Φ [%]	19.6 (\pm 0.68)
Height of fiber bundle in warp direction, h_{warp} [m]	1.5×10^{-4} (\pm 0.04×10^{-4})
Height of fiber bundle in weft direction, h_{weft} [m]	1.1×10^{-4} (\pm 0.04×10^{-4})
Distance between bundles in warp direction, l_{warp} [m]	4.8×10^{-4} (\pm 0.27×10^{-4})
Distance between bundles in weft direction, l_{weft} [m]	6.5×10^{-4} (\pm 0.41×10^{-4})
Macroscopic permeability in warp direction, K_x [m ²]	4.01×10^{-10} (\pm 3.94×10^{-11})
Macroscopic permeability in weft direction, K_y [m ²]	5.39×10^{-11} (\pm 5.73×10^{-12})
Width of fiber bundle in warp direction, w_{warp} [m]	5.7×10^{-4} (\pm 0.16×10^{-4})
Width of fiber bundle in weft direction, w_{weft} [m]	1.0×10^{-3} (\pm 0.53×10^{-4})
Porosity inside bundle, ϕ_f [%]	48 (\pm 8.1)
Fiber radius r [μm]	4.5

Table 2 Material properties of resin.

Property	Value
Viscosity, μ [Pa s]	0.169
Product of surface energy γ and cosine of contact angle θ_c , ($\gamma \cos \theta_c$) [N/m]	0.025

2.2 Results and discussion

Fig. 2 show the resin impregnation and void formation in the microscopic structures of the fabric for impregnation angle of 30°. The domain surrounded by two warp bundles and two weft bundles is indicated by the red dotted lines. For both impregnation angles considered, the voids formed by air trapping between the bundles were due to the fingering caused by the difference between the inter-bundle and intra-bundle resin flow velocities.

Fig. 3 show the relationship between the void fraction and the resin flow velocity. The void fraction was measured for resin impregnation angles of 0°, 30°, 75°, 90°, and θ_{min} values of 49°. It can be observed from the figure that the void fraction increases with decreasing macroscopic resin flow velocity for all the impregnation angles. This is because the difference between the intra-bundle and inter-bundle flow velocities increases with decreasing macroscopic flow velocity, resulting in an increase in the trapped air [23-25]. In addition, the resin flow velocity at the beginning of void formation was highest for an impregnation angle of 0° and lowest for the minimum-void angle θ_{min} .

Figure 2 Resin impregnation and void formation in the microscopic structure observed by a microscope at impregnation angles of 30°.

Figure 3 Experimentally determined relationship between the flow velocity and the void fraction for different flow directions

3 ANALYTICAL MODEL FOR PREDICTION OF VOID FRACTION

3.1 Void formation

Fig. 4 is a schematic of a unit cell of the fabric used to develop the void fraction prediction model. The unit cell is representative of the 2D makeup of the fabric, and comprises two weft bundles and two warp bundles. We defined the unit cell produced by the bundles, crimp, and inter-bundle cavities.

The resin impregnation process of the unit cell used for developing the void fraction prediction model is shown in Fig. 5. The first stage shown in Fig. 5(a), at which time the impregnation begins when the macroscopic flow front reaches one of the crimps in the unit cell. At this time, the macroscopic flow front makes contact with the lower fiber bundle at the red dotted line as shown in Fig. 5(a). The resin impregnation thereafter progresses to the second stage shown in Fig. 5(b). At this stage, the resin impregnation in the transverse fiber bundle on the upstream side of the unit cell is completed, and the impregnation in the inter-bundle cavity begins as indicated by the red dotted line in Fig. 5 (b). The resin impregnation then progresses to the third stage shown in Fig. 5(c). The intra-bundle resin impregnation in the unit cell is completed earlier than the inter-bundle impregnation owing to the difference between the respective resin flow velocities. After completion of the intra-bundle resin impregnation, the progress of the inter-bundle impregnation ceases, and the air trapped in the inter-bundle cavity forms a void. It should be noted that we modeled the inter-bundle impregnation path as the sum of the impregnation of the upstream transverse bundle and the impregnation of the inter-bundle cavity surrounded by fiber bundles. Based on the void formation, we also determined the impregnation paths for Patterns 1 and 2 for the cases of small and large impregnation angles, respectively, as shown in Fig. 6. The detailed impregnation path for each pattern will be modeled in Sections 3.2 and 3.3.

Figure 4 Unit cell of the woven fabric used for the void fraction prediction model

Figure 5 Stages of resin impregnation in the unit cell

3.2 Intra-bundle impregnation path

The intra-bundle resin flow velocity in each warp and weft bundle is given by Eq. (1), which is based on Darcy's law, with the added term of the capillary pressure gradient [20, 24].

$$u = -\frac{k}{\mu\phi_{cr}} \left(\frac{\partial P}{\partial r} - \frac{\partial P_c}{\partial l} \right) \quad (1)$$

where r is the distance from the inlet, P is the pressure at the flow front, μ is the viscosity of the resin, P_c is the capillary pressure in the intra-fiber bundle, ϕ_{cr} is the porosity of the crimp, and l is the intra-bundle impregnation distance. k is the permeability of each warp and weft bundle, and is dependent on the permeability of the crimp [26]. The permeability of the crimp is determined by the ratio of the thickness of the longitudinal fiber bundle to the thickness of transverse bundle, as well as the permeabilities of the warp and weft bundles in both directions:

$$k = \frac{h_{\parallel}k_{\parallel} + h_{\perp}k_{\perp}}{h_{\parallel} + h_{\perp}} \quad (2)$$

where h_{\parallel} and h_{\perp} are respectively the heights of each bundle in the bundling and transverse directions; and k_{\parallel} and k_{\perp} are the permeabilities in the axial and transverse directions of a fiber bundle, and are determined by the Gebart model as expressed by Eqs. (3) and (4), respectively [27].

$$k_{\parallel} = \frac{8r_f^2}{C_{\parallel}} \frac{\phi_{cr}^3}{(1-\phi_{cr})^2} \quad (3)$$

$$k_{\perp} = C_{\perp} r_f^2 \left(\sqrt{\frac{V_{fmax}}{1-\phi_{cr}}} - 1 \right)^2 \quad (4)$$

where r_f is the radius of the fiber filament; and C_{\parallel} , C_{\perp} , and V_{fmax} are the shape functions. The fibers

are assumed to be hexagonally arranged; hence, $C_{\parallel} = 53$, $C_{\perp} = 16/9\pi\sqrt{6}$, and $V_{f_{\max}} = \pi/\sqrt{6}$. In addition, the section of the fabric is homogenized in the gap between the molds to form the 2D model. ϕ_{cr} is the average porosity of the gap between the molds in the crimp, and is given by

$$\phi_{cr} = 1 - \frac{h_{\parallel} + h_{\perp}}{H} (1 - \phi_f) \quad (5)$$

where H is the height of the gap between the molds, and ϕ_f is the porosity of the fiber bundle. It should be noted that the porosity of the fiber bundle is assumed to be the same in both directions [23, 28].

In addition, the capillary pressure in Eq. (1) is determined using the Young-Laplace equation presented as Eq. (6) [29].

$$P_c = \frac{2\gamma C \cos\theta_c}{r_c} \quad (6)$$

where γ is the surface tension of the resin, C is the geometric correction factor, θ_c is the contact angle between the resin and the fiber, and r_c is the capillary radius of the fiber bundle given by Eq. (7). The average porosity in the gap between the molds ϕ is given by Eq. (8).

$$r_c = \frac{\phi}{1 - \phi} r_f \quad (7)$$

$$\phi = 1 - \frac{h}{H} (1 - \phi_f) \quad (8)$$

where h is the height of the bundle in the warp or weft direction.

The intra-bundle impregnation distance Δl is different for Patterns 1 and 2 as indicated by the yellow arrow in Fig. 6. It should be noted that, although there are upper and lower intra-bundle impregnation paths, we used the lower impregnation path, which is longer, to calculate the intra-bundle impregnation distance because it determines the intra-bundle impregnation time. Moreover, for simplicity, we assumed that the two intra-bundle impregnation fronts contact each other at the middle point of the downstream transverse bundle. The intra-bundle impregnation distances for the two patterns are given by Eqs. (9) and (10).

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Pattern 1: } \theta < \theta_{min} \quad & \Delta l_{warp} = l_{warp} + l_{weft} \tan\theta \\ & \Delta l_{weft} = l_{weft} / 2 \\ & \Delta l_{warp} = l_{warp} / 2 \end{aligned} \quad (9)$$

$$\text{Pattern 2: } \theta > \theta_{min} \quad \Delta l_{weft} = l_{weft} + l_{warp} \tan\left(\frac{\pi}{2} - \theta\right) \quad (10)$$

By integrating Eq. (1), each intra-bundle impregnation time $\Delta t(\Delta l)$ is obtained as expressed by Eq. (11) as the time required for the resin to cover a distance Δl in each warp and weft bundle.

$$\Delta t(\Delta l) = -\frac{\mu\phi_{cr}}{k(\partial P/\partial r)} \left(\Delta l + \frac{P_c}{(\partial P/\partial r)} \ln \left(1 - \frac{(\partial P/\partial r)}{P_c} \Delta l \right) \right) \quad (11)$$

The total intra-bundle resin impregnation time Δt_{total} is given by Eq. (12).

$$\Delta t_{total} = \Delta t_{warp}(\Delta l_{warp}) + \Delta t_{weft}(\Delta l_{weft}) \quad (12)$$

The intra-bundle impregnation time increases with the impregnation angle for Pattern 1, whereas the reverse is the case for Pattern 2. The minimum-void angle θ_{min} is the angle at which the relationship between the lengths of the intra-bundle resin impregnation times in Patterns 1 and 2 is reversed. In other words, the angle that satisfies the following equation is the minimum-void angle θ_{min} :

$$\Delta t_1 - \Delta t_2 = 0 \quad (13)$$

where Δt_1 and Δt_2 are the intra-bundle impregnation times for Patterns 1 and 2, respectively.

3.3 Inter-bundle impregnation path and void formation

Assuming that the resin flow velocity through the inter-bundle cavity is the same as the macroscopic flow velocity, the macroscopic resin flow velocity U_n in the inter-bundle cavity in the impregnation direction would be as expressed by Eq. (14), based on Darcy's law.

$$U_n = -\frac{K_n}{\mu\Phi_n} \frac{\partial P}{\partial r} \quad (14)$$

where K_n is the permeability in the resin impregnation direction, and Φ_n is the sectional porosity in the resin impregnation direction. The subscript n indicates the resin impregnation direction at the flow front. Considering the minuteness of the unit cell, if the resin flow velocity during the resin impregnation in the inter-bundle cavity is constant, the resin impregnation time in the inter-bundle cavity for an arbitrary angle ΔT_{inter} can be expressed as follows:

$$\Delta T_{inter} = \frac{L}{U_n} = -\frac{\mu\Phi_n (l_{warp} \cos \theta + l_{weft} \sin \theta)}{K_n (\partial P / \partial r)} \quad (15)$$

where L is the length of the inter-bundle cavity in the flow direction, and l_{warp} and l_{weft} are respectively the distances between the fiber bundles in the warp and weft directions (see Fig. 4).

In addition, resin impregnation between the fiber bundles begins after completion of that in the transverse bundle shown in Fig. 5, and the impregnation time of the fiber bundle is added to the inter-bundle impregnation time. It should be taken into consideration that the impregnation of a fiber bundle begins from two crimps, the impregnation distances of the transverse bundle are given by Eq. (16), and the impregnation time ΔT_{bundle} of the transverse bundle is given by Eq. (17).

$$\Delta L_{bundle} = \begin{cases} l_{weft}/2 & \text{in Pattern1} \\ l_{warp}/2 & \text{in Pattern2} \end{cases} \quad (16)$$

$$\Delta T_{bundle} = t(\Delta L_{bundle}) = -\frac{\mu\phi_{cr}}{k(\partial P / \partial r)} \left(\Delta L_{bundle} + \frac{P_c}{(\partial P / \partial r)} \ln \left(1 - \frac{(\partial P / \partial r)}{P_c} \Delta L_{bundle} \right) \right) \quad (17)$$

Since the resin impregnation of the transverse bundle begins from the crimp and the inter-bundle cavity as shown in Fig. 5(a), a correction coefficient is added to the impregnation time of the transverse bundle. It is thought that the impregnation time of the transverse bundle changes with the ratio of the domain impregnated by the flow from the crimp, the correction coefficient of the impregnation time of the transverse bundle, C_{tb} , is given by Eq. (18). This correction coefficient is calculated by the ratio of the time taken by the resin flow from the crimp to impregnate the fiber bundle in the bundling direction to the time taken by the resin flow from the inter-bundle cavity to impregnate the fiber bundle in the transverse direction.

$$C_{Tb} = \left(1 - \frac{\Delta T_{bundle}}{(w_{bundle}/U_n)} \right) \quad (18)$$

where w_{bundle} is the width of the transverse bundle. This is because of the consideration that the transverse bundle is impregnated by only the resin flow from the inter-bundle cavity in the domain of the negative value, the correction coefficient determined $C_{Tb} = 0$. From Eqs. (2), (17), and (18), the inter bundle impregnation time ΔT is given by

$$\Delta T = \Delta T_{inetr} + C_{Tb} \Delta T_{bundle} \quad (19)$$

Assuming regularity and continuity of the unit cell, the mean value of the void fraction V_v of the unit structure is given by Eq. (19) [21].

$$V_v = \left(1 - \frac{\Delta t_{total}}{\Delta T_{total}} \right) \Phi \quad (20)$$

where Φ is the macroscopic porosity of the fabric.

4 VALIDATION OF ANALYTICAL PREDICTION MODEL

The prediction model was used to determine the void fraction. The material properties of the fabric and resin used for the model are given in Tables 1 and 2. Based on fitting of the experimental data, the geometric correction factor C of the capillary pressure was determined to be 2.5. In addition, a resin infusion point radius r_0 of 0.003 m and gap between the molds H of 0.0003 m were used for the model calculations.

Using Eq. (13), the minimum-void angle θ_{min} in the prediction model was determined to be 52° . There is little deviation between the minimum-void angle calculated by the prediction model and that determined by experiment. The difference between the impregnation angles is very small for the elliptical shape, and it can thus be concluded that the minimum-void angle θ_{min} predicted by the model is in good agreement with the experimentally determined value. The analytically obtained curves of the void fraction as a function of the logarithm of the resin flow velocity is shown in Fig. 8. The theoretical and experimental results are in good agreement, thereby validating the void fraction prediction model.

Figure 8 Relationship between the flow velocity and the void fraction for different flow directions.

5 CONCLUDING REMARKS

We performed experimental 2D radial-injection VaRTM using anisotropic plain-woven fabric. We measured the relationship between the void fraction and the resin flow velocity for an impregnation direction inclined at an arbitrary angle to the fiber bundling direction. We also observed the void formation as a function of the resin impregnation angle in the microscopic structure of the fabric. Our

observations revealed that the void formation process varied with the resin impregnation angle, and that void formation was least for the minimum-void angle, which corresponded to the border between the two void formation patterns. Based on the variation of the void formation with the resin impregnation angle in the microscopic structure of the fabric, we developed a model for predicting the void fraction for arbitrary values of the resin impregnation angle and velocity in the anisotropic fabric. The model can also be used to predict the minimum-void angle for which void formation is least. The predictions of the model were compared with experimental results and good agreement was observed.

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